

A Binary Logistic Regression Model for Assessing the Risk Factors Associated with *Diabetes Mellitus* among Farmers in Benue State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to assess the predisposing factors of diabetes mellitus among farmers in Benue state, using binary logistic regression model. A convenience sampling technique was employed to collect data from 254 patients attending Federal Medical Centre Makurdi (FMC) through case folder reviews and structured interviews. Statistical analyses included summary statistics, proportions, percentages, and binary logistic regression. The socio-demographic profile of respondents revealed a female predominance (135; 53.1%) in the study area, with the largest age group (87; 34.2%) being 45-54 years and an average age of approximately 53 years with a standard deviation of approximately 13 years ($SD \approx 13$). The majority of the respondents had attained secondary education (131; 51.6%), were employed (137; 53.9%), and were married (192; 75.6%). Regarding diabetic status, 224 respondents (88.2%) were diabetic. The binary logistic regression analysis identified several factors significantly associated with an increased likelihood of the occurrence of diabetes among the study population, including age ($B = 1.479$, $p = 0.003$), dietary habits ($B = 0.575$, $p = 0.002$), smoking ($B = 1.412$, $p = 0.003$), family history of diabetes

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($B = 0.602$, $p = 0.000$), alcohol consumption ($B = 0.810$, $p = 0.004$), hypertension ($B = 0.875$, $p = 0.000$), cholesterol level ($B = 0.718$, $p = 0.000$), and body mass index (BMI) ($B = 0.199$, $p = 0.002$). Conversely, employment status ($B = -0.727$, $p = 0.007$), educational level ($B = -0.230$, $p = 0.000$), and income level ($B = -0.853$, $p = 0.000$) were associated with a reduced likelihood of the occurrence of diabetes among the study population. The study recommends promoting lifestyle modifications, enhancing public awareness and screening, improving healthcare access, strengthening socioeconomic support, and implementing community based interventions to reduce diabetes risk and prevalence

Key words: Binary; Diabetes, Risk factors; Farmer;

1. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) represents a significant and growing public health concern globally, particularly in low and middle income countries like Nigeria. The increasing prevalence of diabetes is driven by a complex interplay of genetic, behavioral, socioeconomic, and environmental factors. Understanding the predisposing factors within specific populations is crucial for developing targeted interventions to reduce the disease burden.

In Nigeria, few localized studies have employed advanced statistical methods to identify key risk factors for diabetes. This study aims to assess the risk factors associated with diabetes mellitus among farmers in Benue state, using binary logistic regression analysis. According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), the prevalence of diabetes in Nigeria is approximately 3.9%, with a projected increase to 6.7% by 2045 (IDF, 2021). Benue State, located in the north central region of Nigeria, bears a high burden of diabetes, with a prevalence rate of 4.4% (NBS, 2019). Farmers in Benue State are particularly vulnerable to diabetes due to their occupation, lifestyle, and limited access to quality healthcare. The risk factors associated with diabetes among farmers in Benue State are not well understood, making it difficult to develop effective prevention and management strategies.

This study aims to assess the risk factors associated with diagnosis of diabetes among farmers in Benue State using a binary logistic regression model. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i) evaluate the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents,
- ii) fit a binary logistic model to the incidence of diabetes given the risk factors, and
- iii) predict the odds of diabetes in the study population based on the identified risk factors.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycemia resulting from inadequate insulin production, insulin resistance, or both. Globally, the prevalence of DM has reached alarming levels. According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), over 537 million adults were living with diabetes in 2021, and this number is projected to rise to 643 million by 2030 (International Diabetes Federation, 2021). In sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in Nigeria, the diabetes burden is increasing due to urbanization, sedentary lifestyles, unhealthy diets, and limited access to healthcare services.

Binary logistic regression analysis has been widely employed in epidemiological research to investigate the relationship between various risk factors and the presence of diabetes. This method is especially suitable for modeling dichotomous outcomes such as the presence or absence of disease and allows estimation of the odds of disease occurrence based on multiple predictor variables.

For instance, Imad *et al.* (2021) utilized binary logistic regression in a study involving diabetic and non-diabetic individuals to develop a predictive model for early diabetes detection based on known risk factors. The outcome demonstrated the strong predictive capability of the model. Significant predictors included age above 35, obesity, smoking, hypertension, cholesterol levels, and family history of diabetes, which aligns with global risk profiles.

Assefa and Shifera (2022) conducted a cross-sectional study in Ethiopia using binary logistic regression to identify factors associated with undiagnosed diabetes. Their findings indicated that

increased age, higher BMI, and urban residence significantly increased the likelihood of diabetes. The study underscored the need for improved community level screening efforts across sub-Saharan Africa.

In Nigeria, Adedoyin *et al.* (2013) applied binary logistic regression to data from the Nigerian Demographic and Health Survey to assess the relationship between socioeconomic status and diabetes risk. The analysis revealed that individuals with higher income and education levels were less likely to develop diabetes, highlighting the protective influence of socioeconomic factors.

Similarly, Joshi and Dhakal (2021) employed both logistic regression and a decision tree model to predict type 2 diabetes. The analysis identified five key predictors; glucose levels, number of pregnancies, BMI, diabetes pedigree function, and age. The logistic model achieved a prediction accuracy of 78.26% and a cross validation error rate of 22.86%. The study emphasized the relevance of predictive analytics in diabetes prevention and policymaking.

Onwuka *et al.* (2022) conducted a study in northern Nigeria to evaluate diabetes risk factors using binary logistic regression. The result of the analysis identified increased age, sedentary lifestyle, and hypertension as major predictors of diabetes. Moreover, education and income were protective, suggesting that socioeconomic upliftment could aid diabetes prevention.

Rastogi and Singh (2019) also applied binary logistic regression to assess diabetes risk factors. Their findings indicated that male gender, unhealthy dietary habits, smoking, and high BMI significantly increased the odds of developing diabetes. The study reinforced the need for targeted interventions focused on modifiable behavioral risk factors.

Ghadeer *et al.* (2024) developed a prediction model using logistic regression to determine diabetes status based on diagnostic data. The model achieved an 82% prediction accuracy, demonstrating strong potential for clinical application in early diagnosis and risk stratification.

Furthermore, Ahmadi *et al.* (2021) designed a logistic regression model using an Iranian dataset to predict the probability of diabetic foot ulcers among diabetes patients. Key predictors included

age ($B1 = 0.133$), BMI ($B2 = 0.194$), fasting blood sugar ($B3 = 0.011$), HDL ($B4 = 0.118$), and insulin dependency ($B5 = 0.986$), with a pretest probability of 30.83% and an AUC of 0.914. These results validated the model's applicability for clinical use in risk assessment and management.

Collectively, these studies demonstrate the value of binary logistic regression in identifying significant predictors of diabetes and emphasize the importance of integrating medical, lifestyle, and socioeconomic factors into disease prediction models. By adopting a similar analytical approach, the present study aims to contribute to this growing body of knowledge by focusing on a unique and under represented population; farmers in Benue State, Nigeria.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Data Source

Data for this study were obtained from three primary sources:

1. **Clinical records** : Existing medical records were reviewed to extract clinical data, including diabetes status, blood pressure, and indicators of dyslipidemia.
2. **Questionnaires** : Structured questionnaires were administered to collect socio-demographic and lifestyle information from the participants.
3. **Anthropometric measurements**: Standardized procedures were used to obtain height, weight, and calculate Body Mass Index (BMI).

A total of 254 participants were purposively selected from the Federal Medical Centre, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. All participants gave informed consent prior to data collection, and ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board.

3.2 Methods of Data Analysis

The following statistical methods were employed for data analysis:

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- **Descriptive statistics** were used to summarize socio-demographic characteristics and clinical variables.
- **Binary logistic regression analysis** was performed to identify the risk factors significantly associated with diabetes mellitus.
- **Odds ratios (ORs)** with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were computed to evaluate the strength of associations between predictor variables and diabetes status.

All statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 25.0, and significance was determined at $p < 0.05$.

3.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and describe the characteristics of the dataset. Measures such as the mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage were computed to provide an overview of the socio-demographic and clinical variables.

The **mean** of a given dataset was calculated using the formula:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad (1)$$

The sample standard deviation is given as:

$$\hat{\sigma} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{t=1}^n (x_t - \bar{x})^2} \quad (2)$$

where \bar{x} is the sample mean, n is the sample size.

This measure was used to summarize continuous variables such as age, height, weight, and BMI.

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3.3 Model Specification

The model adopted for this study is the binary logistic regression model and it is stated as

$$p = 1 / (1 + e(\beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_nx_n)) \quad (3)$$

where:

p is the predicted probability of the positive outcome ($p \in [0,1]$)

e is the base of the natural logarithm (approximately 2.718)

β_0 is the intercept or constant term

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n$ are the coefficients of the predictor variables

x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are the predictor variables

The log-odds of the outcome is:

$$\log(p/(1 - p)) = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_nx_n \quad (4)$$

The odds ratio (OR) is the exponentiation of the coefficient:

$$OR = \exp(\beta) \quad (5)$$

3.4 Model Evaluation and Diagnostic Checks

To assess the adequacy and performance of the logistic regression model, the following evaluation methods were employed:

3.4.1 Likelihood Ratio Test

The **likelihood ratio test (LRT)** evaluates whether each predictor significantly contributes to the model. It compares the likelihood of the full model with that of a reduced (null) model. A significant result ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$) indicates that the predictor significantly improves model fit.

High values of the chi-square statistic from the likelihood ratio test suggest a strong partial relationship between the predictor and the outcome, after adjusting for other variables. The test statistic is computed as:

$$= \frac{\text{likelihood of null model}}{\log \text{likelihood of model with the variables}} \quad (6)$$

3.4.2 Wald Statistic

The **Wald statistic** tests the significance of individual regression coefficients.

The Wald statistic W_j is calculated as:

$$W_j = \frac{\hat{\beta}_j^2}{[SE(\hat{\beta}_j)]^2} \quad (7)$$

Where $\hat{\beta}_j$ represent the estimated coefficient of β and $SE(\hat{\beta}_j)$ is its standard error.

A significant Wald statistic indicates that the variable contributes meaningfully to the model.

3.4.3 Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE)

The **maximum likelihood estimator** is used to estimate the model coefficients (β) by maximizing the probability of observing the given data. The log-likelihood function for binary logistic regression is expressed as:

$$\ell(\beta) = \sum [y_i \log(p) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - p)] \quad (8)$$

where:

$\ell(\beta)$ is the log-likelihood function

β are the model coefficients

y_i is the observed binary response (0 or 1)

p is the predicted probability of the positive class ($p = 1 / (1 + e^{(-z)})$)

z is the linear combination of predictors ($z = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_n x_n$)

e is the base of the natural logarithm (approximately 2.718)

Σ denotes the summation over all observations ($i = 1$ to n)

3.4.4 Confidence Interval

Odds ratios were reported with **95% confidence intervals (CIs)** to assess the precision of the estimated effects. A narrow confidence interval suggests high precision, while a wide interval indicates low precision. Unlike p-values, confidence intervals do not directly indicate statistical significance unless they exclude 1.0.

3.4.5 Hosmer–Lemeshow Goodness-of-Fit Test

The **Hosmer–Lemeshow test** evaluates the agreement between observed and predicted outcomes. The predicted probabilities are grouped into deciles, and a Pearson chi-square statistic is computed by comparing observed and expected frequencies:

$$H = \sum_{g=1}^{10} \frac{(O_g - E_g)^2}{E_g} \quad (9)$$

In the above formula, O_g and E_g denote the observed events, and expected events for g^{th} risk deciles group respectively. The test statistic asymptotically follows a chi-square distribution with 8 (number of group minus two) degree of freedom.

Small values (*with large value closer to 1*) indicate a good fit to the data, therefore, good overall model fit. Large values (*with $p - value < 0.05$*) indicate a poor fit to the data.

3.4.6. The Omnibus tests of model coefficients

This test assesses whether the logistic regression model with predictors significantly improves the prediction of the outcome variable compared to the null (constant-only) model. This test evaluates the overall model fit by examining whether the inclusion of predictor variables contributes significantly to explaining the variance in the outcome

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive statistics

The result of the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents reported in Table 1 showed that; among the 254 respondents, 135 (53.1%) were female. The most represented age group was 45–54 years (87; 34.2%), with a mean age of 53 years ($SD \approx 13$). Most participants had secondary education (131; 51.6%), were employed (137; 53.9%), and were married (192; 75.6%).

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Respondent's Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	119	46.9
	Female	135	53.1
	Total	254	100
Age (in years)	25-34	17	6.7
	35-44	55	21.7
	45-54	87	34.2
	55-64	50	19.7
	65 and Above	45	17.7
	Mean±SD	51.7±12.5	
	Total	254	100

Educational Qualification	None	16	6.3
	Primary	72	28.3
	Secondary	131	51.6
	Tertiary	35	13.8
	Total	254	100
Employment Status	Employed	137	53.9
	Unemployed	117	46.1
	Total	254	100
Marital Status	Married	192	75.6
	Single	62	24.4
	Total	254	100
Diabetic Status	Diabetic	224	88.2
	Non-Diabetic	30	11.8
	Total	254	100

Table 2, shows the prevalence of the anthropometric characteristics in the study area, and the result shows that 3 (1.2%) of the respondents are underweight ($BMI < 18.49kg/m^2$), about 122 (48%) of the respondents have normal weight ($BMI = 18.50 - 24.99kg/m^2$), the number of respondents with overweight (possibility of being obese) is 87 (34.3%) ($BMI = 25.00 - 29.99kg/m^2$). Whereas, the prevalence of obesity among the respondents is 42 (16.5%) ($BMI > 30kg/m^2$). Overweight and obesity are the risk factors of diabetic mellitus. Based on the World

Table 2: Anthropometric Characteristics of the Respondents

BMI	Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Underweight	$<18.49kg/m^2$	3	1.2
Normal weight	$18.50-24.99kg/m^2$	122	48.0
Overweight	$25.00-29.99kg/m^2$	87	34.3
Obese	$>30kg/m^2$	42	16.5
Total		254	100

Health Organization's classification of 2004, majority of the respondents 129 (50.8%) in the study area are liable to suffer from diabetes.

4.2 Investigating the Risk Factors of Diabetes using Binary Logistic Regression Model .

The result of the classification table for the constant only model is reported in Table 3.

Table 3: The Constant Only (Null) Model

		B	S.E.	Wald	df	p-value	Exp(B)
Step 0	Constant	2.010	0.194	106.935	1	0.000	7.467

From the result of the constant-only (null) model reported in Table 3, the value of the constant is 2.010, representing the log-odds of the outcome (e.g., having diabetes) when no predictor variables are included. The p-value is 0.000, indicating that the constant is statistically significant at conventional thresholds (e.g., $p < 0.05$). This suggests that the intercept contributes meaningfully to the prediction of the outcome variable. The odds ratio, 7.467, indicates that the odds of the outcome (e.g., having diabetes) are 7.467 times higher than the baseline odds when no predictors are included in the model. The null model suggests that, in the absence of predictors, the likelihood of the outcome is significantly greater than chance, as indicated by the statistically significant constant and the high odds ratio. However, since this model does not include any predictors, its utility is limited, and its performance will serve as a baseline for comparison with more comprehensive models that incorporate explanatory variables.

The Omnibus tests of model coefficients assess whether the logistic regression model with predictors significantly improves the prediction of the outcome variable compared to the null (constant-only) model. This test evaluates the overall model fit by examining whether the inclusion

of predictor variables contributes significantly to explaining the variance in the outcome. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

		Chi-square	df	p-value
	Step	38.974	11	0.000
Step 1	Block	38.974	11	0.000
	Model	38.974	11	0.000

From the result of the Omnibus tests of model coefficients reported in Table 4, the value of the step Chi-Square is 38.975; this value represents the improvement in the model fit at the current step, as predictors are added. It indicates that the model with predictors explains significantly more variance than the null model.

The Omnibus tests of model coefficients shows that the inclusion of the 11 predictors significantly improves the model’s ability to predict the outcome variable compared to the null model. This result confirms that the predictors collectively provide valuable information for explaining the outcome and warrant further investigation into their individual contributions.

The Model Summary provides key indicators of the logistic regression model’s fit and explanatory power. It includes the -2 Log Likelihood value, which reflects the model’s overall fit, and pseudo R-squared measures (Cox & Snell R Square and Nagelkerke R Square), which indicate

the proportion of variance in the outcome variable explained by the predictors. The results are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: The Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	145.502 ^a	0.742	0.768

a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 6 because parameter estimates changed by less than 0.001.

From the result of the model summary reported in Table 5, the value of -2 Log Likelihood is 145.502; this value measures the lack of fit of the model; lower values indicate better model fit. The decrease in the -2 Log Likelihood value from the null model suggests that the model with predictors better fits the data. The Cox & Snell R Square value of 0.742 provides an estimate of the variance explained by the model. However, it does not reach a theoretical maximum of 1, limiting its interpretability in logistic regression. The Nagelkerke R Square is a modified version of the Cox & Snell R Square that adjusts for the maximum possible value, making it easier to interpret. A Nagelkerke R Square value of 0.768 indicates that approximately 76.8% of the variance in the outcome variable is explained by the model.

The model summary shows that the logistic regression model provides a good fit to the data, with a high proportion of variance explained (Nagelkerke R Square = 0.768). This indicates that the predictors included in the model collectively explain a substantial amount of the variance in the outcome variable. The successful convergence further confirms the stability of the parameter estimates.

The Hosmer and Lemeshow test evaluate the goodness-of-fit for a logistic regression model by comparing the observed and predicted probabilities of the outcome variable across deciles of risk. This test determines whether the model adequately fits the data. A non-significant result ($p > 0.05$) suggests that the model's predictions are consistent with the observed data. The results are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6: Hosmer and Lemeshow Test for the Full Model

Step	Chi-Square	Df	P-value
1	6.518	8	0.589

The classification table for the full model provides a detailed assessment of the logistic regression model's predictive performance, comparing observed and predicted outcomes for the dependent variable (e.g., diabetes status).

Table 7: Classification Table for the Full Model

	Observed		Predicted		
			Diabetes Status		Percentage Correct
			No	Yes	
Step 1	Diabetes Status	No	7	23	23.3
		Yes	2	222	99.1
Overall Percentage					90.2

- a. is included in the model
- b. The cut value is 0.500

From the result of the classification table for the full model reported in Table 7, it shows excellent overall performance, with 90.2% accuracy, and performs particularly well in predicting “Yes” (diabetes) cases, with 99.1% correct predictions. However, the model’s ability to predict “No” cases (non-diabetes) is limited, with only 23.3% accuracy, suggesting potential imbalance or other factors influencing the predictions. These results highlight the model’s strength in identifying diabetic cases.

4.2.1 Parameter estimates of the binary logistic regression model

The Parameter Estimates reported in Table 8 presents the results of the full binary logistic regression model. It shows how each independent variable (predictor) influences the likelihood of the outcome variable (e.g., diabetes status) while controlling for all other variables. Key metrics include the regression coefficient (B), standard error (S.E.), Wald statistic, p-value, odds ratio (Exp(B)), and the 95% confidence interval (CI) for Exp(B). These results provide insights into the direction, strength, and significance of each variable's relationship with the outcome.

Table 8: Parameter Estimates of the Full Binary Logistic Model

Variable	B	S.E.	Wald	Df	p-value	Exp(B)	95% CI for Exp(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Age	1.479	0.490	9.126	1	0.003	4.389	0.087	0.595
EmploySta	-0.727	0.322	5.097	1	0.007	0.483	0.298	1.473
LevelofEdu	-0.230	0.023	100.0	1	0.000	0.794	0.513	1.229
Dietaryha	0.575	0.182	9.981	1	0.002	1.777	0.219	1.448
Smokeha	1.412	0.469	9.055	1	0.003	4.105	1.636	10.29
FHistory	0.602	0.149	16.33	1	0.000	1.826	0.757	4.403

Aconsumpt	0.810	0.285	8.078	1	0.004	2.247	0.869	5.812
Hypertens	0.875	0.253	11.96	1	0.000	2.399	0.141	1.232
IncomeL	-0.853	0.242	12.42	1	0.000	0.426	0.116	0.959
Cholesterol	0.718	0.152	22.31	1	0.000	2.050	1.179	3.331
BMI	0.199	0.062	10.30	1	0.002	1.220	0.977	2.247
Constant	0.260	2.728	0.009	1	0.924	1.297		

a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: Age, Employment status, Level of Education, Dietary habits, Smoking habit, Family History of Diabetes, Alcohol Consumption, Hypertension Status, Income Level, Cholesterol Level, Body Mass Index.

The result of the parameter estimates of the full binary regression model as presented in table 8 shows that the Significant risk factors positively associated with diabetes included:

- Age (B = 1.479, p = 0.003), Dietary habits (B = 0.575, p = 0.002), Smoking (B = 1.412, p = 0.003), Family history of diabetes (B = 0.602, p = 0.000), Alcohol consumption (B = 0.810, p = 0.004), Hypertension (B = 0.875, p = 0.000), Cholesterol level (B = 0.718, p = 0.000), Body mass index (BMI) (B = 0.199, p = 0.002), Protective (inverse) associations were observed for: Employment status (B = -0.727, p = 0.007), Educational level (B = -0.230, p = 0.000), Income level (B = -0.853, p = 0.000).

The study identified a range of modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors associated with diabetes mellitus. Older age, poor dietary habits, smoking, alcohol consumption, and

comorbidities such as hypertension and hypercholesterolemia significantly increased diabetes risk. Meanwhile, higher education, gainful employment, and better income levels appeared to provide a protective effect, possibly due to improved health literacy and access to healthcare

4.2.2 Odds predictions for the occurrence of Diabetes among Individual Predictors

Table 9 presents the odds predictions for the occurrence of diabetes (Yes/No) based on different levels of the independent predictors. The table compares the odds for “Low” (low probability of having diabetes) and “High” (high probability of having diabetes) for each predictor variable. The odds are calculated using the formula $Odds = e^{\beta_0 + \beta_i x_i}$, $i=0,1$, where β_0 is the intercept, β_i are the coefficients for the predictors, and x_i are the values of the predictors for an individual.

Table 9: Odds Predictions for No/Yes Occurrence of Diabetes for Individual Predictors

Independent variables	Low	High
Age	1.2969	6.2902
Employment Status	1.2969	0.6269
Level of Education	1.2969	1.0305
Dietary Habits	1.2969	2.3048
Smoking Habit	1.2969	5.3228

Family History of Diabetes	1.2969	2.3679
Alcohol Consumption	1.2969	2.9154
Hypertension Status	1.2969	3.1112
Income Level	1.2969	0.5527
Cholesterol Level	1.2969	2.6591
Body Mass Index (BMI)	1.2969	1.5825

Note: Odds = $e^{\beta_0 + \beta_i x_i}$, $i=0,1$.

The result in table 9, shows that variables such as age, smoking habit, dietary habits, hypertension, alcohol consumption, family history of diabetes, body mass index, and cholesterol level have strong association with higher odds of developing diabetes. Conversely, employment status, level of education and income level are linked to lower odds of diabetes, reflecting protective or mitigating factors. These odds provide valuable insights for understanding the relative importance of different risk factors in diabetes prevention and intervention strategies.

5. CONCLUSION

This study extensively examined the predisposing factors associated with diabetes mellitus among farmers attending the Federal Medical Centre (FMC) Makurdi using a binary logistic regression model. The findings revealed that diabetes remains a pressing public health concern in the region,

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with a high prevalence rate of 88.2% among the sampled patients. The analysis identified multiple significant predictors of diabetes, notably older age, poor dietary habits, smoking, alcohol consumption, family history of diabetes, hypertension, high cholesterol levels, and increased body mass index (BMI). These findings underscore the multifactorial nature of diabetes, where both lifestyle and genetic factors interplay to elevate disease risk.

Importantly, the study also found that higher levels of education, employment, and income were inversely associated with the likelihood of developing diabetes. This suggests that socioeconomic status plays a protective role, potentially by enabling healthier lifestyle choices, better access to healthcare services, and increased health literacy.

Overall, the results of this study emphasize the urgent need for targeted interventions in the region. Recommendations include promoting healthy lifestyles through public education campaigns, increasing community-based screening and early detection efforts, enhancing access to quality healthcare, and addressing socioeconomic disparities. By implementing these strategies, stakeholders can work toward reducing the burden of diabetes and improving health outcomes among populations at risk in Makurdi and similar settings.

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